

CITRATE COMPLEX OF CADMIUM

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The citrate complexes of cadmium have been studied by p_H titration method. Three complexes, one neutral (C) and two anionic (C_1^- and C_2^{2-}) containing one citrate ligand per atom of cadmium, have been found to be formed. The equilibrium constant of the reactions $Cd^{2+} + H_3Cit \rightleftharpoons C + 2H^+$ (I) $C \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$ (II) and $C_1^- \rightleftharpoons C_2^{2-} + H^+$ (III) are respectively 6.43×10^{-7} , 1.59×10^{-5} and 4.86×10^{-9} . The hydroxyl group of the citrate ligand reacts but the proton is not liberated. The probable structures of the complexes C, C_1^- and C_2^{2-} have been discussed.

Citrate and tartrate are very interesting ligands. The utilisation of the alcoholic group in the formation of complex with trivalent antimony has been reported (Das and Pani, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 537; Samantara and Pani, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 165). A proton is usually liberated from the hydroxyl group due to such reactions. Cadmium has been reported to have a less tendency to form complex with oxygen than is observed with zinc (Sidgwick, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Clarendon Press, 1950, p. 275). It would therefore be of interest to study the citrate complex of cadmium.

Polarographic study of cadmium citrate complex has been done by Meites (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3727). The reaction $Cd^{2+} + C_6H_5O_7 \rightleftharpoons CdC_6H_5O_7 + 2H^+$ has been investigated by potentiometric method and the equilibrium constant has been reported to be 5.70×10^{-4} at 25° (Shin Shuzuki, *Sci. Rpts. Res. Inst. Tohoku Univ.*, 1953, 5A, 16). All these investigations do not provide a clear picture of the system at different p_H , and no attempt has been made for a structural representation of the complex. The investigation of citrate complex of cadmium done by p_H titration is described below.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The chemicals used were of Analar quality. p_H of the solution was measured by a Marconi p_H -meter.

Experiment (I).—The solution (105 c.c.) containing cadmium sulphate (0.0025 g. mol.), citric acid (0.003 g. mol.) and KNO_3 (0.025 g. mol.) and another solution (105 c.c.) containing KNO_3 (0.025 g. mol.) and citric acid (0.003 g. mol.) were titrated against 0.5N-NaOH solution. KNO_3 was added to maintain very nearly the same ionic strength in both the solutions. The results are graphically shown respectively by the curves (B) and (A) in Fig. 1. The temperature was $33^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. A white precipitate of cadmium hydroxide was obtained in the system containing cadmium salt above p_H 4.8 and a portion of the precipitate dissolved near about p_H 7.0 No such precipitate was obtained in another experiment containing a large excess of citric acid compared to cadmium (Fig. 2: curve A represents the p_H titration of 175 c.c. of

solution containing 0.0125 g. mol. of citric acid and B that of the same volume of solution containing the same amount of citric acid and 0.00125 g. mol. of cadmium sulphate against *N*-NaOH). It is evident from Figs. 1 and 2 that acid is liberated due to the reaction of cadmium with citrate ligand even at lower p_H . The horizontal distance, which is a measure of the amount of the acid liberated, increases at first with increasing p_H and then decreases. Above p_H 6.5, the horizontal distance is negligible.

D I S C U S S I O N

Let A and B be two points on the same p_H axis intersecting the curves (A) and (B) respectively. The reaction taking place in the solution containing no cadmium is neutralisation of citric acid whereas in the other solution the complex is formed besides the neutralisation of citric acid. Let $[H_3Cit]_A$, $[H_2Cit^-]_A$, $[HCit^{2-}]_A$ and $[Cit^{3-}]_A$ be respectively the molar concentration of citric acid, dihydrogen citrate ion, monohydrogen citrate ion and citrate ion at A. Let $[Ct]_A$ and $[NaOH]_A$ be respectively the molar concentration of total citrate and sodium hydroxide added at A. The concentrations at B are similarly expressed. The concentration of hydrogen ion being the same at A and B is represented by $[H^+]$. Let k_1 , k_2 and k_3 be respectively the first, the second and the third dissociation constant of citric acid ($k_1 = 8.32 \times 10^{-4}$, $k_2 = 4.07 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_3 = 3.24 \times 10^{-8}$; Schwarzenbach and Ackermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 1682).

At B the formation of the complex which takes place besides the neutralisation of citric acid may be represented by

C is the complex and the charge, if any, is not shown. The equilibrium constant is given by equation (3-1) where $[C]$ and $[Cd^{2+}]$ are respectively the molar concentrations of the complex and the cadmium ion at B.

$$\frac{[C] \times [H^+]^n}{[Cd^{2+}] \times [H_3Cit]_B} = K \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3-1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At B,} & \quad [\text{NaOH}]_B + [\text{H}^+] = n[\text{C}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-]_B + 2[\text{HCit}^{2-}]_B + 3[\text{Cit}^{3-}]_B \\ \text{or} & \quad [\text{NaOH}]_B + [\text{H}^+] = n[\text{C}] + a \times [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B \quad \dots \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Subtracting equation (1) from (4) one gets

$$\begin{aligned} & \quad [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A = n[\text{C}] + a ([\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B - [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_A) \\ \text{or} & \quad \Delta[\text{NaOH}] = n[\text{C}] + a \Delta[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}] \quad \dots \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again,} & \quad [\text{Ct}]_B = [\text{C}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B + [\text{HCit}^{2-}]_B + [\text{Cit}^{3-}]_B \\ \text{or} & \quad [\text{Ct}]_B = [\text{C}] + b [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B \quad \dots \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Subtracting equation (2) from (6) one gets

$$\begin{aligned} & \quad [\text{Ct}]_B - [\text{Ct}]_A = [\text{C}] + b ([\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B - [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_A) \\ \text{or} & \quad \Delta[\text{Ct}] = [\text{C}] + b \Delta[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}] \\ \text{or} & \quad \Delta[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}] = \frac{1}{b} (\Delta[\text{Ct}] - [\text{C}]) \quad \dots \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the value of $\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]$ from equation (7), the equation (5) reduces to

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

When the formation of the complex is complete, the concentration of the complex is equal to the concentration of cadmium sulphate $[\text{CdSO}_4]$. Hence

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{CdSO}_4]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{Ct}]_A$, $[\text{Ct}]_B$, $[\text{NaOH}]_A$ and $[\text{NaOH}]_B$ are calculated from the curves in Fig. 1. $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $\Delta[\text{Ct}]$, $[\text{CdSO}_4]$ and a/b are calculated at different p_n .

Substituting these in equation (9), the value of n is obtained. The value of n is very nearly 2 at p_n 4.2 and less than 2 towards the lower p_n range and more than 2 towards the higher p_n range.

Assuming n to be two below p_n 4.2, $[\text{C}]$ is calculated by equation (8). $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{C}]$ from $[\text{CdSO}_4]$. The equilibrium constant of the reaction (3) is calculated by equation (3-1). The values are shown in Table I. The mean value of the equilibrium constant is 6.43×10^{-7} .

TABLE I

p_n	a/b	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^3$	$-\Delta[\text{Ct}]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{CdSO}_4]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_B$ $\times 10^3$	$K \times 10^7$
2.8	0.3585	2.27	1.300	2.315	1.191	2.196	1.726	11.00
3.0	0.4822	3.10	1.700	2.290	1.750	2.115	1.379	7.55
3.2	0.6738	3.91	2.400	2.267	2.503	2.017	1.082	5.27
3.4	0.7034	5.61	3.100	2.241	3.653	1.876	0.660	4.47
3.6	0.9069	6.87	4.300	2.212	5.211	1.691	0.4396	3.68
3.8	1.150	9.83	5.700	2.185	9.114	1.274	0.2245	5.10
4.0	1.203	12.02	6.900	2.155	11.680	0.987	0.1108	6.74
4.2	1.282	11.93	6.700	2.146	12.570	0.889	0.07731	6.80

For the p_n range above 4.2, n is calculated at different p_n values by equation (9), substituting the corresponding values of $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $\Delta[\text{Ct}]$, a/b and $[\text{CdSO}_4]$. The values, thus obtained, are recorded in Table II

n being greater than 2, the formation of the complex C is complete and the increase in proton to cadmium ratio is due to the reaction,

the equilibrium constant of which is given by

$$\frac{[\text{C}_1^-] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-1)$$

where $[\text{C}_1^-]$ is the molar concentration of the complex C_1^- . The whole of the cadmium in the solution would be present partly as C and partly as C_1^- . Hence,

$$[\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] = [\text{CdSO}_4] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Due to the formation of C and C_1^- from cadmium ion and citric acid, respectively, two and three protons are liberated. The total proton liberated due to the formation of the complexes is equal to $2[\text{C}] + 3[\text{C}_1^-]$. Hence,

$$\frac{2[\text{C}] + 3[\text{C}_1^-]}{[\text{CdSO}_4]} = n$$

or

$$\frac{2([\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-])}{[\text{CdSO}_4]} + \frac{[\text{C}_1^-]}{[\text{CdSO}_4]} = n$$

$$\text{or } \frac{[C_1^-]}{[CdSO_4]} = n - 2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{[C]}{[CdSO_4]} = 3 - n \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

The equilibrium constant K_1 of the reaction (10) can be calculated by substituting $[C_1^-]/[CdSO_4]$ and $[C]/[CdSO_4]$ instead of the exact values of $[C_1^-]$ and $[C]$ respectively in equation (10-1). The values of K_1 , thus calculated, are shown in Table II, the mean value being 1.59×10^{-5} .

TABLE II

p_H	a/b	$\Delta[NaOH] \times 10^3$	$-\Delta[C] \times 10^4$	$[CdSO_4] \times 10^3$	n	$K_1 \times 10^5$
4.35	1.487	1.358	7.70	2.116	2.1831	1.00
4.40	1.531	1.429	8.20	2.110	2.2674	1.45
4.45	1.573	1.421	8.20	2.104	2.3097	1.59
4.50	1.614	1.416	8.30	2.101	2.3517	1.72
4.55	1.659	1.409	8.00	2.095	2.3950	1.84
4.60	1.703	1.402	8.00	2.092	2.4383	1.96

The precipitate obtained above p_H 4.8 is cadmium hydroxide (it is free from citrate). The formation of cadmium hydroxide results from the competition of hydroxyl ion and citrate ligand for the small amount of cadmium ion in solution. The free citrate ligand in the system is small and very nearly constant. The increase of p_H introduces increasing amount hydroxyl ion in the solution and, hence, at $p_H > 4.8$, the solubility product of $Cd(OH)_2$ is exceeded. In presence of a large excess of citrate ligand $Cd(OH)_2$ is not precipitated as the concentration of cadmium ion is small and the solubility product of $Cd(OH)_2$ is not reached. It is, however, strange to note that in presence of excess of citrate, the precipitate of $Cd(OH)_2$ is not obtained even by increasing the concentration of OH^- ion hundred to thousand times (at p_H 6.8 or 7.8). Another reaction probably takes place at a higher p_H . To investigate the system at higher p_H the following method was adopted.

Experiment (II).—A solution (75 c.c.) containing KNO_3 (0.025 g. mol.) and sodium citrate (0.005 g. mol.) was titrated against 0.05M-HCl in one experiment and 0.05M cadmium sulphate solution in another experiment. The results are shown in curve (A) and (B) respectively in Fig. 3. (The experimental temperature was $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$). The p_H 's of both the systems are lowered, but the rate of decrease in the system to which hydrochloric acid is added is greater. Broken line in the curve indicates precipitation.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

The reactions taking place in the system to which hydrochloric acid is added is the neutralisation of the acid by the basic citrate ion, and formation of HCit^{2-} , H_2Cit^- and H_3Cit . In the other system to which cadmium sulphate is added, a proton is liberated due to the reaction of cadmium ion with citrate ion. A doubly charged anionic complex C_2^{2-} is formed before the precipitate separates out from the solution.

Since at the beginning the citrate ion present in the solution is in large excess compared to the amount of cadmium added, the condition for complete formation of the complex exists and the proton equivalent to the amount of cadmium sulphate added is expected to be liberated if no other reaction takes place, and the p_{H} of the two systems, at least in the beginning, is expected to be the same for the same amount (molar) of hydrochloric acid and cadmium sulphate added. This is, however, not observed. The deviation is not due to incomplete formation of the complex, as there is evidence of complete formation of C and C_1^- at lower p_{H} even in presence of a small excess of citrate. It is therefore very probable that the complex C_2^{2-} is more basic than citrate ion and a major portion of the proton liberated by reaction (14) is removed by reaction (15), and very little of HCit^{2-} , H_2Cit^- and H_3Cit is formed.

The complex C_1^- is an acid weaker than HCit^{2-} . The dissociation constant is given by equation (15.1).

$$\frac{[C_2^{2-}] \times [H^+]}{[C_1^-]} = K_2 \dots \dots \dots (15-1)$$

where $[C_2^{2-}]$ is the molar concentration of the complex C_2^{2-} . The concentration of citrate being large compared to the cadmium sulphate added, the whole of the cadmium would be present partly as complex C_2^{2-} and partly as C_1^- .

Let x and y be two points on curves (A) and (B) respectively on the same p_H axis. The concentrations of the ions are represented as before. The concentration of hydrogen ion, being the same at x and y , is expressed as $[H^+]$. It can be shown as before that

$$[Ct]_x = [Cit^{3-}]_x \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_3} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_2.k_3} + \frac{[H^+]^3}{k_1.k_2.k_3} \right)$$

or $[Ct]_x = x [Cit^{3-}]_x \dots \dots (16)$

$$[Ct]_y = [C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}] + x [Cit^{3-}]_y$$

or $[Ct]_y = [CdSO_4] + x [Cit^{3-}]_y \dots \dots (17)$

$$[HCl]_x = [H^+] + [Cit^{3-}]_x \times \left(\frac{[H^+]}{k_3} + 2 \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_2.k_3} + 3 \frac{[H^+]^3}{k_1.k_2.k_3} \right)$$

or $[HCl]_x - [H^+] = y [Cit^{3-}]_x \dots \dots (18)$

Since the complex C_2^{2-} is first formed and then with a proton a portion of it is converted to C_1^- .

Total acid liberated at $y = [CdSO_4]$.

$$[CdSO_4] = [H^+] + [C_1^-] + y [Cit^{3-}]_y$$

or $[CdSO_4] - [C_1^-] = [C_2^{2-}] = [H^+] + y [Cit^{3-}]_y \dots \dots (19)$

From equations (16) and (17) one gets

$$[Ct]_x - [Ct]_y = x ([Cit^{3-}]_x [Cit^{3-}]_y) - [CdSO_4]$$

or $\Delta[Ct] = x \Delta[Cit^{3-}] - [CdSO_4] \dots \dots (20)$

From equations (18) and (19) one gets

$$[HCl]_x - [C_2^{2-}] = y \Delta[Cit^{3-}] \dots \dots (21)$$

From equations (20) and (21) one gets

$$\Delta[Ct] = \frac{x}{y} ([HCl]_x - [C_2^{2-}]) - [CdSO_4]$$

or $\frac{\frac{x}{y} [HCl]_x - [CdSO_4] - \Delta[Ct]}{(x/y)} = [C_2^{2-}] \therefore \dots \dots (22)$

$[H^+]$; $[HCl]_x$, $[Cit]_y$ and $[CdSO_4]$ are obtained from the curves in Fig. 3 x/y and $\Delta[Cit]$ are calculated and $[C_2^{2-}]$ is obtained from equation (22). $[C_1^-]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C_2^{2-}]$ from $[CdSO_4]$. The values of K_2 , calculated by equation (15-1), are collected in Table III. The average value of the equilibrium constant is 4.86×10^{-9} . The results confirm the assumption that C_2^{2-} is a stronger base, i.e., C_1^- is a weaker acid than $HCit^{2-}$. It is interesting to note that even at p_H 7.5 $[C_1^-]$ is ten times greater than $[C_2^{2-}]$. It is possible to convert the complex into C_2^{2-} by titrating against sodium hydroxide and roughly know the concentration of C_1^- in the solution. The following experiment was done to demonstrate C_1^- behaving as a monobasic acid.

TABLE III

p_H	x/y	$\Delta[Cit] \times 10^3$	$[HCl]_x \times 10^4$	$[CdSO_4] \times 10^3$	$[C_1^-] \times 10^3$	$[C_2^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$K_2 \times 10^9$
7.50	103.40	1.97	1.992	1.675	1.511	1.641	3.43
7.45	92.32	2.94	3.311	2.531	2.259	2.719	4.27
7.40	82.35	3.65	3.969	3.125	2.810	3.147	4.46
7.35	73.53	4.47	4.624	3.818	3.469	3.496	4.50
7.30	65.60	5.29	5.277	4.490	4.111	3.785	4.62
7.25	58.59	6.08	5.929	5.114	4.712	4.019	4.80
7.20	52.30	6.97	6.580	5.883	5.465	4.180	4.83
7.15	46.77	8.13	7.228	6.898	6.433	4.673	5.14
7.10	41.77	8.89	9.162	7.578	7.057	5.211	5.87
7.00	33.40	11.27	12.350	9.677	9.069	6.084	6.71

The solution (145 c.c.) containing 0.025 g. mol. of KNO_3 , 0.01 g. mol. of sodium citrate and 0.001 g. mol. of cadmium sulphate was titrated against 0.1N-NaOH solution. The results are shown in curve (B) in Fig. 4. Curve (A) represents the results obtained with another solution with the same conditions as the previous one except that there is no cadmium sulphate. Curve (B) is very similar to the neutralisation curve of an acid. It is of interest to note that the neutralisation point is reached at about 11 c.c. of alkali. The p_H attained by the solution containing cadmium due to the addition of 11 c.c. of alkali is reached by the other solution on addition of 1 c.c. of the same alkali; 10 c.c. of alkali, i.e., 0.001 g. mol. of NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.001 g. mol. of cadmium sulphate.

Structure of the Complex

Fig. 2 indicates that the undissociated carboxyl group in citrate ligand existing at lower p_H are induced to ionise due to the complex formation. No proton is, however, liberated from the hydroxyl group as the two curves converge near about neutralisation point. The results therefore do not indicate whether the hydroxyl group is joined to the central cadmium atom or not. If the hydroxyl group is not joined to the cadmium atom, the three carboxyl groups of citrate ligand cannot give a complex of sufficient stability as five- or six-membered ring cannot be formed. For the formation of a stable complex the hydroxyl group should be attached to the central atom. The oxygen atom in the

hydroxyl group may donate a pair of electrons even if the proton is not ionised. Probably such a thing happens in the citrate complex of cadmium.

The complex C may be represented by the following structure in which the citrate ligand occupies three co-ordination positions and the fourth position is occupied by a molecule of water, the presence of which is necessary to explain the formation of C_2^{2-} . The co-ordination number of cadmium in complex has been reported to be both four and six. If co-ordination number six is more favoured by cadmium in the citrate complexes, two more water molecules might be present in the structures given below. Two different structures of each complex are probable since the three carboxyl groups of citrate ligand are not similar and it is not possible to predict which of the two carboxyl groups reacts.

The carboxyl group in complex C dissociates as the p_H is increased to give C_1^- . The structure of C_1^- may be represented by

The complex C_2^{2-} dissociates above p_H 7 to H^+ and C_2^{2-} . The water molecule present in the co-ordination sphere dissociates. The structure of C_2^{2-} may be represented by

If, however, the proton liberated from C_1^- to give C_2^{2-} comes from the hydroxyl group attached to the cadmium atom, the structure of C_2^{2-} may be represented by

(Complex C_2^{2-})

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